

Extractive spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) using 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneisonicotinoylhydrazone

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Abstract : The extraction of V^V with 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneisonicotinoylhydrazone (HMAINH) has been studied. The method is simple, rapid and highly accurate. The reagent forms a yellow colored 1 : 1 molar ratio complex (V : HMAINH). The complex shows absorption maximum at 400 nm, where as absorption due to reagent is negligible. The Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 20–30.0 ppm of vanadium(V). Optimum detection range as defined by Ringbom's plot was found to be 7.0–20.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of extracted species were found to be $1.15 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 44 ng cm^{-2} , respectively. The standard deviation was found to be ± 0.11 . The effect of various diverse ions on the estimation of vanadium is described. The proposed method has been successfully applied to the determination of vanadium in urine samples.

Keywords : HMAINH, extraction, vanadium determination, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Vanadium is a trace element of highly critical role in biochemical processes and of significant importance in environmental, biological analysis due to its toxicity. Vanadium in trace amounts is an essential element for cell growth, also has been shown to inhibit cholesterol synthesis and to increase the oxidation of fatty acids of higher concentrations. It is excreted through urine. The amount of vanadium in blood and urine depends upon intensity and duration of exposure. Vanadium has also been reported as the index element in urban environmental pollution, especially air pollution. The toxicity of vanadium is dependent on its oxidation state with vanadium(V) being more toxic than vanadium(IV)¹. Therefore, the development of a new spectrophotometric method for the selective extraction and determination of vanadium is of great importance. Several spectrophotometric methods for determination of vanadium have been reported²⁻¹⁶.

Among various methods of analysis, spectrophotometry is preferred as a versatile technique in exploring the use of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneisonicotinoylhydrazone (HMAINH) as an effective reagent to determine vanadium at micro level, in diverse materials and substances. Further, the colour of the extracted metal

complex is found remain stable for a considerable period, which sometimes extends even more than 48 h. Hence, it was thought of interest to develop a simple, rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method for vanadium. In the present paper the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of V^V with HMAINH is reported. The use of this reagent may prove to be advantageous as it can be synthesized at low cost with high yield and of best purity.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectrum and optimization of analytical parameters :

The absorption spectrum of the V^V -HMAINH complex in chloroform shows the absorption maxima at 400 nm, whereas absorption due to reagent is nearly negligible (Fig. 1). Therefore, all the absorbance measurement was taken at 400 nm against the solvent blank in spectrophotometric determination of vanadium.

Fig. 1. (A) Absorption spectrum of V^V -HMAINH against reagent blank, (B) absorption spectrum of HMAINH against chloroform.

The extraction behaviour of vanadium(v)-HMAINH complex in terms of substance was investigated over the pH range 1–10, keeping all other conditions constant. The results obtained from pH studies indicate that maximum extraction of vanadium occurs in the pH range 1.81–1.89 (Fig. 2). In recommended procedure a citrate buffer of pH 1.87 gives satisfactory pH control and does not interfere in the determination in any way.

Various organic solvents were examined for the extraction of vanadium-HMAINH complex and it was observed that the extraction of vanadium(v) complex was quantitative in chloroform. The solvents can be arranged in the decreasing order of their extraction coefficients as chloroform > xylene > toluene > ethyl acetate > MIBK > benzene > hexane.

The effect of reagent concentration was studied by varying the volume of 0.025% HMAINH. It was observed that absorbance remains nearly constant from 3 to 4 mL (Fig. 3). Hence 3 mL of reagent was recommended for determination of vanadium(v) for the further studies.

Fig. 2. Extraction of V^V -HMAINH as a function of pH.

Fig. 3. Effect of reagent HMAINH concentration on the absorbance of V^V in chloroform.

The study of change in absorbance with variation in equilibrium time required for the complete extraction showed that at least 90 s was necessary. The extracted complex was found to be stable for 48 h.

Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 5–30 ppm of vanadium at 400 nm (Fig. 4). Optimum range as defined by Ringbom's plot was 7–20 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were calculated to be $1.146 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 44 ng cm^{-2} respectively at 400 nm.

Fig. 4. Calibration plot of V^V with HMAINH (Beer's law).

The stoichiometry of the extracted species was determined by carrying out Job's continuous variation method (Fig. 5) and was further confirmed by mole ratio method (Fig. 6) and shows 1 : 1 molar ratio of reagent : cation. The stability constant of the complex was found to be 5.62×10^5 .

The effect of the various foreign ions were investigated in order to find tolerance limit of these ions in the extraction of V^V . No interference was observed in the

Fig. 5. V^V -HMAINH species by Job's continuous method

Fig. 6. Mole ratio for V^V -HMAINH species.

presence of following ions at the amounts (mg mL^{-1}) shown as Cl^- (3000), Br^- (2800), I^- (2800), Al^{III} (150), Cu^{II} (40).

For the study of reproducibility and accuracy of the method, absorbance measurement with ten different identical solutions containing 20 ppm of vanadium was determined. Average of these ten readings and standard deviation was calculated. The standard deviation was found to be 0.11. From standard deviation reproducibility of results with 95% confidence limit was 20.0 ± 0.1 .

Application :

Urine sample was analyzed for vanadium. It tested negative hence to this sample, known amount of vanadium were added and analyzed by the proposed procedure for vanadium. Result of analysis of sample is reported in the Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of vanadium with HMAINH from urine sample

Sample	Vanadium(V)			Relative error of present method (%)
	Fortified amount (ppm) ^a	Found by present method (ppm) ^a	Found by standard method ²⁰ (ppm) ^a	
	Urine	7.0	6.98	

^aAverage of five determinations.

Determination of vanadium in urine : 50 mL of the urine sample was concentrated to 5 mL, by evaporation. To this solution a known amount of vanadium was added and mixed with 5 mL concentrated HNO_3 and 5 g of potassium sulphate, and heated to dryness. The process was repeated 2–3 times. Then HNO_3 (1 : 3, 25 mL) was added to the residue and digested on a water bath for 30 min¹⁷. The contents were again evaporated to dryness, cooled, and the residue was dissolved in water, filtered, and neutralized with dilute ammonia. The mixture was diluted to a known volume with water. Appropriate aliquots of this solution were taken and the proposed general procedure was followed for the vanadium determination.

Experimental

A digital Systronics 335 pH meter with combined glass electrode and a Systronics 106 spectrophotometer were used for pH and absorbance measurements. All chemi-

cals used were of analytical grade. A stock solution of vanadium (1 mg/mL) was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate (1 mg/mL) in double distilled water. Solutions of lower concentration were obtained by appropriate dilution as required. The stock solution of vanadium(V) was standardized¹⁸. 2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneisonicotinoylhydrazone (HMAINH) was synthesized by known method¹⁹ and a 0.01 M HMAINH solution was prepared by dissolving HMAINH in dimethylformamide and volume made up by ethanol in volumetric flask.

Citrate buffer was used to maintain the pH throughout the experiment. It was prepared by dissolving 5 g of citric acid in 50 mL double distilled water by adding ammonia.

Recommended method :

An aliquot of solution containing 200 μg of vanadium(V) was taken into a flask. To this 3 mL of 0.025% HMAINH solution was added and diluted with citrate buffer (pH 1.8) upto the mark in 25 mL calibrated flask. The solution was transferred into 125 mL separatory funnel, followed by addition of 10 mL chloroform. Two phases were equilibrated for 60 to 90 s. The organic extract was collected over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove the traces of water, then it was transferred in a 10 mL volumetric flask and made up to the mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the extracted complex was measured at 400 nm against a reagent blank prepared in the same way but, without the addition of vanadium(V). A calibration curve was prepared. Unknown amount of vanadium(V) was determined from the calibration curve.

Conclusion :

The 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneisonicotinoylhydrazone (HMAINH) was used as the reagent for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of micro amount of vanadium from synthetic as well as in urine samples. The above reagent provides a simple, rapid and accurate and reproducible method for spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V). It has advantages of high sensitivity, selectivity and easy availability.

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